

OPEN LETTER

The Embassy of Good Science – a community driven initiative to promote ethics and integrity in research [version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 2 approved with reservations]

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V1 First published: 02 Mar 2022, 2:27
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14422.1>
Latest published: 02 Mar 2022, 2:27
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14422.1>

Abstract

The Embassy of Good Science (<https://www.embassy.science>) aims to improve research integrity and research ethics by offering an online, open, 'go-to' platform, which brings together all information on research integrity and research ethics relevant for researchers, and makes that information accessible, understandable, and appealing. It effectively organizes and describes research integrity and research ethics guidelines, educational materials, cases, and scenarios. The Embassy is wiki-based, allowing users to add -- when logged in with their ORCID researcher id -- new information, and update and refine existing information. The platform also makes the research integrity and research ethics community visible and accessible in pages dedicated to relevant initiatives, news and events. Therefore, the Embassy enables researchers to find useful guidance, rules and tools to conduct research responsibly. The platform empowers researchers through increased knowledge and awareness, and through the support of the research integrity and research ethics community. In this article we will discuss the background of this new platform, the way in which it is organized, and how users can contribute.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 1 02 Mar 2022	view		

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Keywords

Research integrity, research ethics, responsible conduct of research, open source, policy, education

This article is included in the [Science with and for Society](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Research Culture](#) collection.

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Author roles: **van Hoof M:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Writing – Original Draft Preparation; **Evans N:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Writing – Review & Editing; **Inguaggiato G:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Writing – Review & Editing; **Marušić A:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Gordijn B:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Dierickx K:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **van Zeggeren D:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Writing – Review & Editing; **Dunnik H:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Writing – Review & Editing; **Gesinn A:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Writing – Review & Editing; **Bouter L:** Conceptualization, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Widdershoven G:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Funding Acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing;

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This research was financially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 741782 [EnTIRE] and 787580 [VIRT2UE].

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

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How to cite this article: van Hoof M, Evans N, Inguaggiato G *et al.* **The Embassy of Good Science – a community driven initiative to promote ethics and integrity in research [version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2022, 2:27 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14422.1>

First published: 02 Mar 2022, 2:27 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14422.1>

Plain language summary

The Embassy of Good Science (<https://www.embassy.science>) aims to improve the conduct of research in Europe and beyond by presenting information of research integrity and ethics in an accessible, understandable and appealing way. The Embassy is wiki-based, allowing anyone to contribute. The platform also brings the research community together in novel ways in a dedicated community section. Therefore, The Embassy enables researchers to find useful guidance, rules and tools to conduct research responsibly. The platform empowers researchers through increased knowledge and awareness, and through the support of the research integrity and research ethics community. In this article we will discuss the background of this new platform, the way in which it is organized and how users can contribute.

Background

The trustworthiness of research results is increasingly being questioned¹. In practice, research often leads to results that cannot be reproduced²⁻⁵. Several internal and external factors of human, operational and methodological origins have been identified⁶. However, their interplay is anything but clear^{7,8}. There is much attention to the classic triad of fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism, partly in response to high profile cases of misconduct⁹⁻¹². However, other factors such as ‘*sloppy science*’ and ‘*questionable research practices*’ seem to have more effect and impact on research and researchers because of the sheer volume of these “small” misdemeanours¹³. Researchers sometimes experience inadequate support from the institutions where they work in ensuring the quality of research. They are often promoted based on superficial outcome measures. The number of publications (‘*publish or perish*’¹⁴), impact factors, citations, patents and the grants received dominate the evaluation and reward of researchers and science¹⁵. The competition between researchers themselves is reinforced by the limited number of places that are available. Within this competitive system, the same researchers are also expected to act as independent judges of the work produced in their field; prior to publication or when awarding a grant, they assess the work of their direct competitors. It seems that individual poor research practices can be associated with common pitfalls and psychological coping mechanisms, adequately captured in the mnemonic TRAGEDIES (*Temptation, Rationalization, Ambition, Group and authority pressure, Entitlement, Deception, Incrementalism, Embarrassment and Stupid systems*)¹⁶.

Without denying current day problems, we are convinced that most researchers want to do their job well, but sometimes lack information about how to recognise the perverse incentives and pressures experienced in hyper-competitive academic environments, or how to find solutions to specific day-to-day practical, methodological and ethical questions. “*The Embassy of Good Science*” (<https://www.embassy.science>)¹⁷ is at the service of every researcher who wants to build up a practice of good research both by increasing knowledge and awareness of the best guidance and practices in research integrity and ethics and by sharing and collaboratively building new knowledge. We do this, for example, by making initiatives within the biomedical

sciences easy to find and understand. In the case of REWARD¹⁸, which aims to reduce waste in (medical) science and promote rigor and reproducibility, we sum up its best practices and make them shareable. The platform has been developed in consultation with stakeholders across Europe, whose needs and preferences are reflected in the platform’s content.

Sharing knowledge, experiences and good practices

The purpose of the Embassy of Good Science is both to inform researchers and to enable them to share experiences and good practices surrounding research integrity and ethics. The Embassy brings together, and makes smart connections between, relevant guidelines and regulations, cases and scenarios, and teaching materials. ‘Theme’ pages provide engaging, bite-sized introductions to single topics related to good research practices, research principles, or misbehaviours. Complex guidance and practices are made accessible by describing why they are important, for whom they are important, and how can they guide the practice of research. Essentially, these theme pages provide the context in which all of the relevant resources on that topic across the platform are brought together and made usable and understandable. Users interested in, for instance ‘p-hacking’, ‘predatory publishing’, or ‘research virtues’, can read a Theme page of the topic, which links to resources (relevant guidance, online training, and misconduct cases) about the topic across The Embassy. Technically, specific information can be filtered and compared per discipline and country. In this way it is possible to organize a wide range of background information, examples of good practices, cases, (inter) national guidelines and regulations.

A dedicated ‘Training’ section provides access to free online training materials and courses, but also gives information about opportunities to follow more traditional in-person courses on integrity issues experienced in practice. The Embassy offers material that can be used by universities to provide training to researchers, (data) managers and other staff. Bespoke ‘Guides’ for training courses can also be constructed and made openly available directly on the platform. Guides consist of step-by-step instruction pages, describing individual exercises or activities, which users can make and group together themselves. The training guide for the European Commission funded VIRT2UE train-the-trainer programme, for example, is presented on The Embassy. VIRT2UE is a blended learning programme which gives trainees the knowledge and skills to conduct a research integrity course from a virtue ethics perspective. The VIRT2UE guide contains separate instruction pages for four series of e-learning modules and individual instruction pages detailing how to facilitate in person participatory exercises. In line with the ethos of the platform, VIRT2UE takes an aspirational approach, and focuses on what it means to be a good and virtuous researcher. The core of the training is to promote reflection on personal attitudes and practices.

The platform also makes the research integrity and ethics communities visible. Projects and consortia can inform, via The Embassy, an existing audience interested in research integrity

and ethics about their initiatives, news and events. The repository function allows them to store their materials – such as reports, guidelines, leaflets - for the long term, allowing smaller initiatives to be represented online on The Embassy's 'Initiatives' page rather than building their own websites from scratch.

Open science

The open-source platform is technically based on and inspired by Wikipedia (Wikimedia Foundation, USA). With approximately 47 million edits in November 2019 alone, and donations of 35 million dollars per year, this is a proven safe, scalable and well-maintained open-source system. Wikipedia is consulted 21 billion times a month worldwide¹⁹. Where there has been discussion for years about the reliability of Wikipedia's content, studies show that it is comparable to traditional encyclopaedias^{20,21}. A review of specialist content, such as content from pharmacology²², shows a similar picture. Meanwhile, with a total of approximately 50 million articles²³, it has most likely become the largest encyclopaedia in human history.

Just like with Wikipedia, the entire content of The Embassy is freely accessible to everyone. In addition, the content can be supplemented and adjusted by users. The only requirement for making an adjustment is an ORCID account (Open Researcher and Contributor ID, ORCID Inc.). Currently, more than 7 million researchers worldwide already have such an ORCID²⁴. To guarantee quality, all changes and additions can be traced at all times and, if necessary, corrected.

An important technical addition to the platform is the Semantic Mediawiki²⁵ extension. This makes it possible to organize content in a smart way ("*semantic web*"). The information is easily searchable and different sources of information can be linked to each other. The system works well for people and machines, according to the FAIR principles²⁶. This also makes it possible to give automated systems access to the knowledge that is collected on the platform. A complete overview of the open-source software used can be found on the platform itself²⁷.

On a wiki-platform it can be difficult for users to create and edit content. A core group of experts provide most of the content and changes to Wikipedia²⁸. To lower the threshold, increase usability and be inclusive, the user interface of The Embassy has been rebuilt from the ground up. It has been designed to be intuitive. We hope that 'passive' users (readers) are encouraged to submit and edit content (see the [video](#)). In the future, substantial digital contributions will be provided with a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) so that the content can be included in the scholarly literature and can be cited. Such micro publications²⁹ create the ability to transparently summarize, assess, discuss, verify, revoke, mix and expand information and knowledge.

The specific extensions and adjustments made by software developers within this project are also open source³⁰. This means that other organizations can reuse elements of the platform in a different configuration, for example by changing the design, structure and content.

The online community moderates itself

Unlike other scientific platforms such as ResearchGate³¹ (Berlin, Germany), The Embassy is not profit making. Compared to, e.g. Retraction Watch³², users have the freedom to moderate the content and submit content themselves. The tone of The Embassy is also positive. We believe that "*Naming and shaming*" of individuals does not contribute to improving research practice or culture. The first content has been developed by the European Commission funded projects EnTIRE³³ and VIRT²UE³⁴. In the coming years, the intention is that the online community will gradually take on further development and moderation. Just as with Wikipedia, there is a risk of incidents of online vandalism³⁵. This is expected to remain a limited problem. During the first year since going live, amongst a total of 7000 edits, just one edit could be considered as non-substantial 'tinkering'. Clear versioning and tracked changes ensure good levels of control and enables editors to undo changes easily. In the case of Wikipedia, a study showed that about half of all entries that were vandalised and had a deletion of more than 90% were repaired within three minutes, while the overall average repair time was 8 days³⁶. A linked ORCID account ensures that the level and field of expertise of community members can be inspected, where relevant, when contributions are verified. Also, in cases of vandalism and a continued breach of the terms and conditions of the platform, users can be selectively blocked based on their ORCID.

Conclusion

The Embassy of Good Science is a platform that has the potential to inform and engage the research community on research integrity and ethics. The platform aims to support individual researchers, but also, thorough increased awareness and action, to incrementally improve the trustworthiness of research and the culture in which research is conducted.

Data availability

No data is associated with this article.

Software availability

Platform available at: www.embassy.science

Front-end design elements: <https://github.com/the-embassy-of-good-science>

Archived front-end design elements: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5925902>³⁷

Back-end design elements: <https://github.com/the-embassy-of-good-science/the-embassy-platform>

Archived back-end design elements: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5925930>³⁸

License: MediaWiki and The Embassy are licensed under the terms of the GNU General Public License, version 2 or later. Derivative works and later versions of the code must be free software licensed under the same or a compatible license. This includes "extensions" that use MediaWiki functions or variables; see <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-faq.html#GPLAndPlugins>

for details. For the full text of version 2 of the license, see: <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-2.0.html>. For full details of the licensing see: <https://github.com/the-embassy-of-good-science/the-embassy-platform/blob/master/COPYING>.

Acknowledgements

EnTIRE aims to create an online platform that makes RE and RI information easily accessible to the research community. The EnTIRE Consortium is composed Amsterdam UMC and VU University, Amsterdam, Gesinn.It, KU Leuven, University of Split School of Medicine, Dublin City University, the Central European University, University of Oslo, University of Manchester, European Network of Research Ethics Committees. The authors would also like to thank the *EnTIRE consortium members*: Alexander Gesinn, Ana Marusic, Andrijana Perković Paloš, Anna, Astrid Hooghiemstra, Bert Gordijn, Bjørn Hofmann, Dirk Lanzerath, Dorothee Gueth, Elsa Amin, Emma Mulder, Ferdy Pullens, Giulia Inguaggiato, Guy Widdershoven, Harald Dunnink, Hugh Desmond, Iris Lechner, Ivan Buljan, Jonathan Lewis, Kim Zandvliet-Oerlemans, Kris Dierickx, Lana Barac, Lisa Tambornino, Marc van Hoof, Mohammad Hosseini, Natalie Evans, Peter Kakuk, Raymond de Vries, Rea Scepanovic, Rosie Hastings, Rúben Nascimento, Ruzica Tokalic, Soren Holm, Stefan Veen, Talitha Ahmed, Tom Lindemann, Vicko Tomic

VIRT2UE aims to develop a sustainable train-the-trainer blended learning programme enabling contextualised research integrity and ethics teaching across Europe focusing on understanding and upholding the principles and practices of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. The VIRT2UE Consortium is composed of the VU Medical Center Amsterdam, KU Leuven, University of Split School of Medicine, Austrian Agency for Research Integrity, University of Oslo, European Network of Research Ethics Committees, Ankara University, National Technical University of Athens, University of Helsinki, University of Latvia, Universidade Catolica Portuguesa, University of Insubria, and Momkai. The authors would also like to thank the *VIRT2UE consortium members*: Ana Marusic, Ana Sofia Carvalho, Andrijana Perković Paloš, Armin Schmolmueller, Astrid Hooghiemstra, Bert Molewijk, Bjørn Hofmann, Costas Charitidis, Daniel Pizzolato, David van Zeggeren, Dirk Lanzerath, Eleni Spyrou, Emma Mulder, Erika Lofstrom, Fenneke Blom, Franca Marino, Giulia Inguaggiato, Harald Dunnink, Ivan Buljan, Jan Helge Solbakk, Joana Araújo, Kim Zandvliet-Oerlemans, Kris Dierickx, Krishma Labib, Lana Barac, Laura Hartman, Lisa Tambornino, Marc van Hoof, Marco Cosentino, Margreet Stolper, Martina Garriga, Mustafa Volkan Kavas, Natalie Evans, Nicole Foeger, Panagiotis Kavouras, Rien Janssens, Rosemarie Bernabe, Rúben Nascimento, Ruzica Tokalic, Signe Mezinska, Solveig Corner, Stefan Veen, Teodora Konach, Vassilis Markakis, Vicko Tomic, Gamze Senyurek

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Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ✓ ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 21 June 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15567.r29460>

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? **Izak van Zyl**

Cape Peninsula University of Technology, Cape Town, South Africa

This open letter discusses a 'community-driven initiative' that houses information about ethics and research integrity in a collaborative virtual space.

I am unsure how the Embassy initiative can bring together "ALL information on research integrity and research ethics relevant for researchers" (emphasis added). The Embassy is wiki-based, meaning that the scope and quality of such information are determined by the scientific community, and more specifically, anyone with an ORCID and access to a computer, with the time, knowledge and energy to do so. This already implies a potential epistemological disconnect, on one hand, between the compilers and readers of the information, as well as a potential power imbalance, on the other. Who would be more inclined to read and contribute? All 26 Embassy founders are to my knowledge based in Europe. The open letter itself acknowledges that the "platform has been developed in consultation with stakeholders across Europe, whose needs and preferences are reflected in the platform's content". If it were to be inclusive, how does this initiative, then, engage communities from the global South? How does it create meaningful opportunities to amplify historically marginalised (scientific) voices?

I find the claim about irreproducibility to be misleading, at best. The concept of reproducibility is not germane in the qualitative, interpretivist, constructivist or critical paradigms. Claiming a universal reproducibility in "science" reinforces the epistemological disconnect (or even bias) I raise above. Then, the article tends to rely on older sources to substantiate some serious 'current' claims – like that of trustworthiness and reproducibility, for example.

I do not know what is meant by the claim that "their interplay is anything but clear". Here, the authors write that human, operational and methodological factors affect the veracity of the research endeavour, which is obviously true. But that their interplay is unclear is not substantiated. Good science – anywhere – is reflective, critical science. This does not mean that instances of 'bad science' will not occur. It means that interplaying factors do not go unnoticed, and many scholars devote meta-analyses toward these.

I do not find the claim that researchers are “often promoted based on superficial outcome measures” to be substantive, and the claim that researchers are rewarded and evaluated purely on measurable outcomes is based on a single study from Hong Kong. Of course, it happens in many universities across the world, but to claim ‘universal superficiality’ is simply false. The link to the so-called TRAGEDIES model is both legitimate and interesting. However, even this model is up for scrutiny as a ‘comment’ and not a peer-reviewed resource.

The Embassy’s vision to share knowledge, experiences and good practices is laudable but ambitious. I am not familiar with this initiative, but I can anticipate it will need critical mass to stimulate uptake. It builds on the Wikipedia model, but this model presents two challenges: 1) how is it economically viable as free and open-source software (FOSS); and 2) how does it guarantee factually correct content across multiple disciplines? In the case of the former, the Wikipedia model is not self-sustainable: it relies on donations. In the case of the latter, the authors use the term “corrected” to guarantee quality, but how will this be/is this done? I am not so concerned about online vandalism as I am about credibility, factuality and veracity. There are also many different interpretations of and approaches to ethics in research. I advocate for something like intersubjective ethics, but this is traditionally at odds with the biomedical model. How are these types of complexities accounted for?

Overall, this is a noteworthy initiative and I look forward to engaging with it in future. It does, however, present serious complexities which I hope the authors can address in future open letters or publications. All the best with this initiative.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Partly

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

No

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Ethics; communication studies; transdisciplinary studies

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 20 June 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15567.r29463>

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Donald Sharpe

University of Regina, Regina, Canada

The paper does a good job of bringing to the attention of the research community the Embassy of Good Science, explaining its objectives and purpose. All of my comments are fairly minor, mostly observations as I read the paper.

The abstract speaks to bringing together “all information on research integrity and research ethics relevant for researchers”. I am not sure “all information” can possibly be collected, especially given what we know changes constantly. The other issue with ethics is frequently there are no right or wrong answers but rather varying opinions. For example, is deception in research good or bad?

The Background section made a few claims, all supported by citations, that nonetheless I struggled with. “Research often leads to results that cannot be reproduced”. What does “often” mean here? Although some efforts to replicate classic findings have failed, many have not. How one defines success or failure here is complicated. And no one has attempted to sample all research to see what the failure rate is.

“[Researchers] are often promoted based on superficial outcome measures... number of publications... impact factors, citations, patents, and the grants received”. I am not sure that many researchers (including myself) would regard these outcome measures to be superficial. Getting publications is hard. Impact factors are a measure of research impact to some extent. Citations do indicate one’s work is being read and incorporated into the literature. Success at obtaining grants and patents should be recognized.

“Perverse incentives and pressures experienced in hyper-competitive academic environments”. That’s a bit strong. Academia has its challenges but many individuals enjoy being in academia, thrive on competition, and appreciate its benefits (monetary and otherwise).

Open Science --- Wikipedia. Perhaps a bit more was said about Wikipedia than is needed here, but the comparison does explain what the authors are striving to achieve.

Overall, interesting paper as an introduction to the Embassy of Good Science.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Yes

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Research methodology, statistics, ethics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 21 March 2022

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15567.r28684>

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The open letter by Van Hoof and colleagues provides a useful overview of the Embassy of Good Science and its structure and ambitions. The Embassy of Good Science promotes the principles and practices of good science through the provision of information, education and practical tools and deserves to be widely known. The letter is clearly written and easily understood. My comments are intended to clarify a small number of issues and suggest additions that would add to the letter's impact.

Major Comments:

1. The letter would greatly benefit from a summary diagram that mirrors the Embassy's website structure. I found myself looking for this diagram as soon as I reached the "Sharing knowledge, experiences and good practices" section (page 3). Descriptions of theme pages, the training section, and statements such as "four series of e-learning modules" (page 3) would all be supported by a summary diagram.
2. "Compared to eg. Retraction Watch, users have the freedom to moderate the content and submit content themselves" (page 4). I was somewhat confused by the comparison with Retraction Watch, as Retraction Watch does not aim to serve the same purpose as the Embassy of Good Science. In this sense, it is perhaps not surprising that Retraction Watch has a different user engagement model.
3. "The tone of the Embassy is also positive" (page 4). When I read this statement, I expected that the Embassy of Good Science does not provide information about research misconduct, but when I visited the website, I found that this information was available. It may be helpful to specify that Embassy of Good Science does provide information about "Misconduct and misbehaviors" as one of 4 themes. Please see comment 1 about the need for a summary diagram.
4. Similarly "We believe that "Naming..." (page 4). Is there any published evidence to support the stated belief that "Naming and shaming of individuals does not contribute to improving research culture of practice"? The term "naming and shaming" is in my view overly simplistic and risks detracting from discussions of misconduct where perpetrators need to be identified.
5. The letter could give more information about (i) the user feedback received to date, (ii) if or how this has supported the development of the material offered by the Embassy of Good Science, and (iii) how often content will be reviewed and updated.
6. Similarly, the letter could describe research that is being done based on the Embassy of Good Science platform and its use and/or opportunities for future research (see for example minor comment 3 below).

Minor comments

1. No references were cited for the two consecutive statements "Researchers sometimes receive inadequate support..." and "They are often promoted based on..." (page 3).
2. "...The Embassy is freely available to everyone" (page 4): "to everyone" could be removed- while well intentioned, there are inevitable restrictions on access, notably the need for access to the internet and to material in English. Some reference could be made about accessibility of content via mobile devices or phones, as this might facilitate access by LMIC users.
3. Is there evidence that "micro publications create the ability to transparently summarise..."? (page 4). Could future research on the use of micro publications by the Embassy of Good Science add to the evidence base here?
4. "The first content has been developed by the European Commission funded" (page 4): It

would be helpful to specify over which years EC funding was available. Please also note “VIRT²UE” as opposed to “VIRT2UE” elsewhere in the text.

5. Similarly, “in the coming years” (page 4): It would be helpful to specify over which timeframe the online community will “gradually take on further development and moderation”, and how this process is envisaged to work. Presumably, there will always be a role for some type of central oversight, so it would be helpful to provide more information about how any transition will occur, and to what extent the model will rely upon ongoing external funding.

Is the rationale for the Open Letter provided in sufficient detail? (Please consider whether existing challenges in the field are outlined clearly and whether the purpose of the letter is explained)

Yes

Does the article adequately reference differing views and opinions?

Partly

Are all factual statements correct, and are statements and arguments made adequately supported by citations?

Partly

Is the Open Letter written in accessible language? (Please consider whether all subject-specific terms, concepts and abbreviations are explained)

Yes

Where applicable, are recommendations and next steps explained clearly for others to follow? (Please consider whether others in the research community would be able to implement guidelines or recommendations and/or constructively engage in the debate)

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Research integrity, biobanking, cancer genetics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.
